

EcoPart specifications

EcoPart is a web application dedicated to particle data from the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) instruments.

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OLD ECOPART description

1. About Ecopart (current)

General introduction (current)

The existing EcoPart application is designed to host data from the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) and the LIIST instruments. It permits to:

- *Load particle data and associate them with CTD data and plankton images loaded and annotated in EcoTaxa*
- *Store quasi raw data from the UVP (LPM & images)*
- *Process size spectra from the particle data*
- *Download the resulting particle spectra, the CTD and the plankton data according to defined permissions*
- *Visualize data and permit their promotion thanks to the internet access*

The new EcoPart application will be designed for UVP data only as no one utilised EcoPart for LISST data till now.

Database status (current)

The people providing the data remain the owner of their data. The datasets can have different status (PRIVATE, PARTIALLY or FULLY AVAILABLE). If the data you are interested to visualize or download are not accessible, you can contact the different project managers and data owners using the links provided in the STATISTICS display.

The data owners are always indicated in the datasets that you download. Please contact them to get additional information and discuss publications.

By default, all particle and CTD data can be displayed in the graph section and limited resolution data downloaded.

Unless the project manager changes the delays, the full particle and CTD data will be available after 24 months from acquisition.

Unless the project manager changes the delays and if the EcoTaxa associated project is annotated and visible, the validated plankton data will be available after 36 months from acquisition.

You can get full access to any dataset (project) by getting annotation or management permission to the associated EcoTaxa annotation project (for UVP projects only).

Warning about the plankton datasets: only validated (e.g. annotation visually checked by experts) are included in the displayed and downloaded datasets. Please check the validation ratio in the statistics page and in the data summary exported with the data. Do not hesitate to visit the EcoTaxa project to check the quality of the annotation.

DB EcoPart :

Liste des relations							
Schéma	Nom	Type	Propriétaire	Persistence	Méthode d'accès	Taille	Description
public	part_ctd	table	postgres	permanent	heap	2174 MB	
public	part_histocat	table	postgres	permanent	heap	290 MB	
public	part_histocat_lst	table	postgres	permanent	heap	6712 kB	
public	part_histopart_det	table	postgres	permanent	heap	2097 MB	
public	part_histopart_reduit	table	postgres	permanent	heap	945 MB	
public	part_projects	table	postgres	permanent	heap	400 kB	
public	part_projects_res	table	postgres	permanent	heap	104 kB	
public	part_samples	table	postgres	permanent	heap	8912 kB	
public	temp_tasks	table	postgres	permanent	heap	448 kB	

(9 lignes)

Part_ctd :

Table « public.part_ctd »				
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut
psampleid	integer		not null	
lineno	integer		not null	
depth	double precision			
datetime	timestamp without time zone			
chloro_fluo	double precision			
conductivity	double precision			
cpar	double precision			
depth_salt_water	double precision			
fcdom_factory	double precision			
in_situ_density_anomaly	double precision			
neutral_density	double precision			
nitrate	double precision			
oxygen_mass	double precision			
oxygen_vol	double precision			
par	double precision			
part_backscattering_coef_470_nm	double precision			
pot_temperature	double precision			
potential_density_anomaly	double precision			
potential_temperature	double precision			
practical_salinity	double precision			
practical_salinity__from_conductivity	double precision			
qc_flag	integer			
sound_speed_c	double precision			
spar	double precision			
temperature	double precision			
extrames01	double precision			
extrames02	double precision			
extrames03	double precision			
extrames04	double precision			
extrames05	double precision			
extrames06	double precision			
extrames07	double precision			
extrames08	double precision			
extrames09	double precision			
extrames10	double precision			
extrames11	double precision			
extrames12	double precision			
extrames13	double precision			
extrames14	double precision			
extrames15	double precision			
extrames16	double precision			
extrames17	double precision			
extrames18	double precision			
extrames19	double precision			

extrames20

Index :

"part_ctd_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid, lineno)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

"part_ctd_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

part_histocat :

Table « public.part_histocat »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
psampleid	integer		not null		plain		
classif_id	integer		not null		plain		
lineno	integer		not null		plain		
depth	double precision				plain		
datetime	timestamp without time zone				plain		
watervolume	double precision				plain		
nbr	double precision				plain		
avgstd	double precision				plain		
totalbiovolume	double precision				plain		

Index :

"part_histocat_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid, classif_id, lineno)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

"part_histocat_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

part_histocat_lst :

Table « public.part_histocat_lst »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
psampleid	integer		not null		plain		
classif_id	integer		not null		plain		

Index :

"part_histocat_lst_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid, classif_id)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

"part_histocat_lst_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

part_histopart_det :

Table « public.part_histopart_det »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
psampleid	integer		not null		plain		
lineno	integer		not null		plain		
depth	double precision				plain		
datetime	timestamp without time zone				plain		
watervolume	double precision				plain		
class01	integer				plain		
class02	integer				plain		
class03	integer				plain		
class04	integer				plain		
class05	integer				plain		
class06	integer				plain		
class07	integer				plain		
class08	integer				plain		
class09	integer				plain		
class10	integer				plain		
class11	integer				plain		
class12	integer				plain		
class13	integer				plain		
class14	integer				plain		
class15	integer				plain		
class16	integer				plain		
class17	integer				plain		
class18	integer				plain		
class19	integer				plain		
class20	integer				plain		
class21	integer				plain		
class22	integer				plain		
class23	integer				plain		
class24	integer				plain		
class25	integer				plain		
class26	integer				plain		
class27	integer				plain		
class28	integer				plain		
class29	integer				plain		
class30	integer				plain		
class31	integer				plain		
class32	integer				plain		
class33	integer				plain		
class34	integer				plain		
class35	integer				plain		
class36	integer				plain		
class37	integer				plain		
class38	integer				plain		
class39	integer				plain		

...45

biovol04	double precision				plain		
biovol05	double precision				plain		
biovol06	double precision				plain		
biovol07	double precision				plain		
biovol08	double precision				plain		
biovol09	double precision				plain		
biovol10	double precision				plain		
biovol11	double precision				plain		
biovol12	double precision				plain		
biovol13	double precision				plain		
biovol14	double precision				plain		
biovol15	double precision				plain		
biovol16	double precision				plain		
biovol17	double precision				plain		
biovol18	double precision				plain		
biovol19	double precision				plain		
biovol20	double precision				plain		
biovol21	double precision				plain		
biovol22	double precision				plain		
biovol23	double precision				plain		
biovol24	double precision				plain		
biovol25	double precision				plain		
biovol26	double precision				plain		
biovol27	double precision				plain		
biovol28	double precision				plain		
biovol29	double precision				plain		
biovol30	double precision				plain		
biovol31	double precision				plain		
biovol32	double precision				plain		
biovol33	double precision				plain		
biovol34	double precision				plain		
biovol35	double precision				plain		
biovol36	double precision				plain		
biovol37	double precision				plain		
biovol38	double precision				plain		
biovol39	double precision				plain		
biovol40	double precision				plain		
biovol41	double precision				plain		
biovol42	double precision				plain		
biovol43	double precision				plain		
biovol44	double precision				plain		
biovol45	double precision				plain		

Index :

"part_histopart_det_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid, lineno)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

"part_histopart_det_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

part_histopart_reduit :

ecopart=# \du+ part_histopart_reduit;

Table « public.part_histopart_reduit »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
psampleid	integer		not null		plain		
lineno	integer		not null		plain		
depth	double precision				plain		
datetime	timestamp without time zone				plain		
watervolume	double precision				plain		
class01	integer				plain		
class02	integer				plain		
class03	integer				plain		
class04	integer				plain		
class05	integer				plain		
class06	integer				plain		
class07	integer				plain		
class08	integer				plain		
class09	integer				plain		
class10	integer				plain		
class11	integer				plain		
class12	integer				plain		
class13	integer				plain		
class14	integer				plain		
class15	integer				plain		
biovol01	double precision				plain		
biovol02	double precision				plain		
biovol03	double precision				plain		
biovol04	double precision				plain		
biovol05	double precision				plain		
biovol06	double precision				plain		
biovol07	double precision				plain		
biovol08	double precision				plain		
biovol09	double precision				plain		
biovol10	double precision				plain		
biovol11	double precision				plain		
biovol12	double precision				plain		
biovol13	double precision				plain		
biovol14	double precision				plain		
biovol15	double precision				plain		

Index :

"part_histopart_reduit_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid, lineno)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

"part_histopart_reduit_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

part_projects :

Table « public.part_projects »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
pprojid	integer		not null	nextval('part_projects_pprojid_seq'::regclass)	plain		
ptitle	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
rawfolder	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
ownerid	integer				plain		
projid	integer				plain		
instrumtype	character varying(50)				extended		
op_name	character varying(100)				extended		
op_email	character varying(100)				extended		
cs_name	character varying(100)				extended		
cs_email	character varying(100)				extended		
do_name	character varying(100)				extended		
do_email	character varying(100)				extended		
prj_info	character varying(1000)				extended		
prj_acronym	character varying(100)				extended		
cruise	character varying(100)				extended		
ship	character varying(100)				extended		
default_instrumsn	character varying(50)				extended		
default_depthoffset	double precision				plain		
oldestsampledate	timestamp without time zone				plain		
public_partexport_deferral_month	integer				plain		
public_visibility_deferral_month	integer				plain		
public_zooexport_deferral_month	integer				plain		
remote_type	character varying(20)				extended		
remote_directory	character varying(200)				extended		
remote_password	character varying(100)				extended		
remote_url	character varying(200)				extended		
remote_user	character varying(100)				extended		
remote_vectorref	character varying(200)				extended		
enable_descent_filter	character(1)				extended		

Index :

"part_projects_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (pprojid)

"is_part_projects_projid" btree (projid)

Référencé par :

TABLE "part_samples" CONSTRAINT "part_samples_pprojid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (pprojid) REFERENCES part_projects(pprojid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

part_projects_res :

public part_projects_res

Table « public.part_projects_res »

Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
pprojid	integer		not null		plain		
ptitle	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
rawfolder	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
ownerid	integer				plain		
projid	integer				plain		
instrumtype	character varying(50)				extended		
op_name	character varying(100)				extended		
op_email	character varying(100)				extended		
cs_name	character varying(100)				extended		
cs_email	character varying(100)				extended		
do_name	character varying(100)				extended		
do_email	character varying(100)				extended		
prj_info	character varying(1000)				extended		
prj_acronym	character varying(100)				extended		
cruise	character varying(100)				extended		
ship	character varying(100)				extended		
default_instrumsn	character varying(50)				extended		
default_depthoffset	double precision				plain		
oldestsampledate	timestamp without time zone				plain		
public_partexport_deferral_month	integer				plain		
public_visibility_deferral_month	integer				plain		
public_zooexport_deferral_month	integer				plain		
remote_type	character varying(20)				extended		
remote_directory	character varying(200)				extended		
remote_password	character varying(100)				extended		
remote_url	character varying(200)				extended		
remote_user	character varying(100)				extended		
remote_vectorref	character varying(200)				extended		
enable_descent_filter	character(1)				extended		

Index :

"part_projects_res__pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (pprojid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

Part_samples :

Table « public.part_samples »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
psampleid	integer		not null	nextval('part_samples_psampleid_seq'::regclass)	plain		
pprojid	integer				plain		
profileid	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
filename	character varying(250)		not null		extended		
sampleid	integer				plain		
latitude	double precision				plain		
longitude	double precision				plain		
organizedbydepth	boolean				plain		
histobrutavailable	boolean				plain		
qualitytaxo	character varying(20)				extended		
qualitypart	character varying(20)				extended		
daterecalculhistotaxo	timestamp without time zone				plain		
windir	integer				plain		
winspeed	integer				plain		
seastate	integer				plain		
nebulousness	integer				plain		
comment	character varying(1000)				extended		
stationid	character varying(100)				extended		
firstimage	integer				plain		
lastimg	bigint				plain		
lastimgused	bigint				plain		
bottomdepth	integer				plain		
yoyo	boolean				plain		
sampledate	timestamp without time zone				plain		
op_sample_name	character varying(100)				extended		
op_sample_email	character varying(100)				extended		
ctd_desc	character varying(1000)				extended		
ctd_origfilename	character varying(250)				extended		
ctd_import_name	character varying(100)				extended		
ctd_import_email	character varying(100)				extended		
ctd_import_datetime	timestamp without time zone				plain		
ctd_status	character varying(50)				extended		
instrumsn	character varying(50)				extended		
acq_aa	double precision				plain		
acq_exp	double precision				plain		
acq_vollimage	double precision				plain		
acq_depthoffset	double precision				plain		
acq_pixel	double precision				plain		
acq_shutterspeed	integer				plain		
acq_smczo	integer				plain		
acq_exposure	integer				plain		
acq_gain	integer				plain		
acq_filedescription	character varying(200)				extended		
acq_eraseborder	integer				plain		
acq_tasktype	integer				plain		
acq_threshold	integer				plain		
acq_choice	integer				plain		
acq_disktype	integer				plain		
acq_smbase	integer				plain		
acq_ratio	integer				plain		
acq_descent_filter	boolean				plain		
acq_pressure_gain	double precision				plain		
acq_xsize	integer				plain		
acq_xsize	integer				plain		
acq_ysize	integer				plain		
acq_barcode	character varying(50)				extended		
proc_datetime	timestamp without time zone				plain		
proc_gamma	double precision				plain		
proc_soft	character varying(250)				extended		
lisst_zscat_filename	character varying(200)				extended		
lisst_kernel	character varying(200)				extended		
lisst_year	integer				plain		
txt_data01	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data02	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data03	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data04	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data05	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data06	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data07	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data08	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data09	character varying(200)				extended		
txt_data10	character varying(200)				extended		
imp_descent_filtered_row	integer				plain		
imp_removed_empty_slice	integer				plain		
proc_process_ratio	integer				plain		
integrationtime	integer				plain		

Index :

- "part_samples_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (psampleid)
- "is_part_samples_prj" btree (pprojid)
- "is_part_samples_sampleid" btree (sampleid)

Contraintes de clés étrangères :

- "part_samples_pprojid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (pprojid) REFERENCES part_projects(pprojid)

Référencé par :

- TABLE "part_ctd" CONSTRAINT "part_ctd_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)
- TABLE "part_histocat_lst" CONSTRAINT "part_histocat_lst_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)
- TABLE "part_histocat" CONSTRAINT "part_histocat_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)
- TABLE "part_histopart_det" CONSTRAINT "part_histopart_det_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)
- TABLE "part_histopart_reduit" CONSTRAINT "part_histopart_reduit_psampleid_fkey" FOREIGN KEY (psampleid) REFERENCES part_samples(psampleid)

Méthode d'accès : heap

temp_tasks :

Table « public.temp_tasks »							
Colonne	Type	Collationnement	NULL-able	Par défaut	Stockage	Cible de statistiques	Description
id	integer		not null		plain		
owner_id	integer				plain		
taskclass	character varying(80)				extended		
taskstate	character varying(80)				extended		
taskstep	integer				plain		
progresspct	integer				plain		
progressmsg	character varying				extended		
inputparam	character varying				extended		
creationdate	timestamp without time zone				plain		
lastupdate	timestamp without time zone				plain		
questiondata	character varying				extended		
answerdata	character varying				extended		

Index :

- "temp_tasks_pkey" PRIMARY KEY, btree (id)

Méthode d'accès : heap

Data provider information (current)

This application is designed to facilitate the processing and the display of the UVP datasets.

A mobile instance will be available (contact : marc.picheral@obs-vlfr.fr) for field processing of your data but the importation of the projects will have to be done again on the server instance when back to shore.

We recommend keeping the default settings for the delays to release your datasets and make the associated EcoTaxa project visible. This will allow the access of the results and the visualization of the images.

Citation and disclaimer (current)

If you use EcoTaxa or EcoPart in your work, we would appreciate that:

- *you cite it as: Picheral M, Colin S, Irisson J-O (2017). EcoTaxa, a tool for the taxonomic classification of images. <http://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr>*
- *you consider setting aside some funds in your next grant to support its maintenance and development. Contact us to estimate what would be both reasonable and useful.*

EcoPart was funded by SOERE MOOSE..... / Development by [Altidev](#)

Disclaimer : *The managers of the EcoTaxa application are not responsible for the safekeeping of the images and associated data it hosts, even if they make their best to keep the application stable and secure.*

2. Status of EcoPart pages and features (current)

Functional (current)

Pages and features (current)

HOME

- Map with samples + statut and infos on clic
- Possibility to filter samples and apply it to the map
- Generate stats on samples/projects selected
- Share page ⇒ mail to + URL link with filters
- Export selection ⇒ page export
- Set up and generate plots
- Section about

LOGIN

- Login EcoTaxa
- Logout

EXPORT

- Statistics on the exported data
- Export format options
- Options for export location

TASK MANAGEMENT

- Task list : import/export
- Task status
- Access a task

TASK SHOW

- Information about the task
- Log file ⇒ opens a txt file containing logs
- If error :

- questions/answers
- restart task
- If successful
 - Export get generated export file
 - import : show log and details
- If in progress : show log and details

PARTICLE PROJECT MANAGEMENT (list of projects)

- Table list of projects
- Mail to dataowner
- Select project
- New project
- Help tool on pages

PROJECT

- help tool on pages
- Import samples
- Remove selected samples
- Edit project metadata
- Actions :
 - Compute detailed histogram
 - Match EcoTaxa samples
 - Compute taxo history
 - CTD import
- Show importation result graph
- Edit samples

EDIT SAMPLES

- Consult sample details
- Edit sample metadata details
- Drop the sample
- Recompute histograms on save

NEW PROJECT

- Help tool on pages
- Select folder on FTP
- Link EcoTaxa project
- Instruments list ⇒ supported instruments : UVP5, UVP6, UVP6remote
- General metadata
- Privacy delay
- Automatic pulling settings
- Create the project

IMPORT SAMPLES

- Help tool on pages
- Import new
- Update samples
- Load only metadata : The purpose of "Load only metadata" checkbox is to just reload metadata of sample

EDIT PROJECT METADATA

- Help tool on pages
- Select folder on FTP
- Link EcoTaxa project
- Instruments list ⇒ supported instruments : UVP5, UVP6, UVP6remote, Lisst
- General metadata
- Privacy/delay
- Automatic pulling settings
- Save
- Cancel
- Remove project : delete project

SHOW IMPORTATION RESULT GRAPH

- Show generated graphs

Tree structure of the site (current)

Ecopart plan du site

Technical (current)

EcoPart DB

⚠ The EcoPart DB files are located in `/home/EcoTaxa/postgresql` (because the 2 applications were previously one).

```
psql -U postgres -d EcoPart -h localhost -p 5435
```

EcoPart App

EcoPart runs as a uwsgi application (see <https://uwsgi-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). Uwsgi allows to overcome some weaknesses (performance level) of python. Uwsgi is a linux service.

```
$ service uwsgi status
```

- uwsgi.service - LSB: Start/stop uWSGI server instance(s)
Loaded: loaded (/etc/init.d/uwsgi; generated)
Active: active (running) since Tue 2022-04-26 04:36:34 UTC;
9min ago

The source is in `/home/ecopart/git` , it is the "master" branch of the git repository:

```
www-data@EcoTaxa:/home/ecopart/git$ git status
On branch master
Your branch is up to date with 'origin/master'.
```

The source belongs to the `www-data` user, mainly for security reasons. So, before any operation on it, you have to switch your shell to `www-data`:

```
root@EcoTaxa:/home/EcoPart# sudo -u www-data /bin/bash
www-data@EcoTaxa:/home/ecopart$
```

 Staying as root to do operations in the directory will not cause any errors at the time, but could be very damaging later (typically during a reboot).

3. Existing link between EcoTaxa and EcoPart (current)

- Link an EcoTaxa project to its multiples EcoPart project
- Export EcoTaxa classification data trough EcoPart export
- Compute classification histogram > ComputeZooMatch
- Generate taxonomy histogram from EcoTaxa
- Generate stats on projects
- Granted user's rights to EcoPart project based on linked EcoTaxa project permissions. (`get_visible_projects`)
- Get current EcoTaxa user (`id / name / email, to : list all / show / create / GetFile / ForceRestart / Clean / GetStatus / autoclean / Monitor task`)
- Login directly to EcoTaxa account, no EcoPart account
- Get taxo tree or taxo sub tree

NEW ECOPART

specifications

4. Entity–relationship model

[Ecopart diagrams](#)

5. Data level definitions

Data Level Definitions:

- **L0-a:** Raw, unprocessed data.(e.g. raw)
- **L0-b:** Enriched raw data with metadata (eg config, meta)
- **L0-c:** Processed raw data (e.g., ecodata or work) with QC flag set to PENDING.
- **L1-a:** Processed raw data with visual QC.
- **L1-b:** Additional QC applied... *TBD (to be defined)*.

6. Use cases of the application

Actors

Who is going to be using the website?

Data creator :

- Want to convert the open format of Zooprocess or UVPapp to a workable format (ex : from number of individuals to abundances).
- Wants to publish its data, in order to make them accessible and bring them a visibility partly linked to the notoriety of the tool.
- Want to ensure the quality of its data and correct it in case of error (QC)

Data consumer :

- Want to consult or download data depending of the project's privacy level

Application administrator :

- Want to manage data and update the application.

Use cases

- UC#0 **Connect** to the web app using EcoPart account
- UC#1 **Display** project(s) to manage from the EcoPart database into the web app
- UC#2 **Create** an EcoPart project from the web app
- UC#3 **Edit** an EcoPart project from the web app (permissions, metadata and imports)
 - UC#3.1 Edit permissions (access control on project)
 - UC#3.2 Edit metadata of the project
 - UC#3.3 Import data in the project
- UC#4 **Explore** data from the EcoPart database into the web app through filtering on samples or project
- UC#5 **Generate** figures of filtered data from the EcoPart database into the web app
- UC#6 **Export** filtered data from the EcoPart database into the web app

- UC#7 **Monitor** task on the system
- UC#8 **Learn** more about EcoPart
- UC#9 **Translate** the web app
- UC#10 **Access help** from any pages

7. User

The user can create an account through the interface, he will then receive an email for validation. In the meantime his account will be **pending**. Then his account will be **valid**, The user as well as the administrator will be able to **deactivate** the user account, passing it to deactivate status.

The user will be able to edit all his info except the email.

He will also be able to change and reset his password.

8. Privacy

Access control on the EcoPart app

- Role that can be granted to any auth user -

Data consumer : can explore and export data any Authenticated user EP

Data producer : can create projects and import data to EcoPart and EcoTAXA, any Authenticated user EP

Application admin : can basically do anything (see all project create read edit export import edit metadata, Access to the administration panel...)

Roles not exclusive : **Data consumer, Data producer, Application admin**

	Explore data	Run Tasks	Create project	Administrate app
Anonym	V	X	X	X

Data consumer	V	V	X	X
Data producer	V	V	V	X
Application admin	V	V	V	V

Access control on Project data

User can be **Anonym** : Unauthenticated user EP

Users can be **User** : Authenticated user EP without any role on the project

- Privilege that can be granted in a project -

Member : Bypass the privacy deadlines (view figures, stats on the project, export particles & EcoTaxa classification data, Import samples)

Manager : Can manage the project (import/export / edit metadata/ manage privilege on the project...), can be multiple managers.

This privilege are exclusive Member<Manager

- **The manager should be able to define data privacy deadlines to secure access to data of his project for a given period of time, the project will have different status depending on these deadlines.** -

(For an authenticated user that have not be granted of any role on the project)

Private : Hidden data, project metadata visible (to request access), can do stats on the project, no other actions allowed

Visible : Project metadata visible (to request access), can do stats on the project, can generate figures on the data, no other actions allowed

Public : Visible & detailed LPM & CTD export : Project data partially exploitable, figure generation ok, detailed LPM & CTD data export allowed

Public + : Visible & detailed LPM & CTD export & EcoTaxa classification: Project 100% exploitable, figure generation ok, detailed LPM & CTD & EcoTaxa classification data export allowed

NB, we decided to suppress this existing status :

Visible & reduced LPM export : The project is visible, can do stats on the project, figure generation ok, reduced LPM & CTD data export allowed

- EcoPart / EcoTaxa rights to collect EcoTaxa classification data -

The EcoPart user will be able to connect multiple EcoTaxa account fetching projects in multiple EcoTaxa instances. EcoTaxa instances will need to have a name or a acronym (ex EU, US, etc.).

When in EcoPart, an EcoPart project is linked to an EcoTaxa project by the manager of the EcoTaxa project, in EcoTaxa we could automatically store that "EcoPart user" can access (read+export) the project. This will allow any member of this EcoPart project to export EcoTaxa classification data and more generally any user with export rights on the EcoPart project to export EcoTaxa classification data from the EcoTaxa linked project.

When linking projects in EcoPart, we will have to inform the user (manager of the EcoTaxa project) that he is giving the export rights to all the user members of the EcoPart project. As the user is connected to his EcoTaxa account from EcoPart, he must be the manager in the EcoTaxa project he wants to link to the EcoPart project, so we want to show the message to him directly in EcoPart without any modification in EcoTaxa.

To keep in mind : we create a strong link between EcoTaxa prj and EcoPart prj, if the linked EcoPart or EcoTaxa project changes for any reason, we will have to handle it.

Unauthenticated API call on protected EcoTaxa resources : security gap.

- EcoPart / EcoTaxa rights update metadata -

Enable update of metadata from EcoPart to EcoTaxa for 'a', 'exp', 'pressure', lat/Lon, date/time and all standardised fields in order to maintain data consistency between the two projects.

-> How to deal with other metadata?

Marc : Correction of the depth of the objects (offset). Implies a management on EcoTAXA side (depth_raw saving) ?

- EcoPart / EcoTaxa link between projects -

One project in EcoPart is linked to one project from the instrument.

It will lead to [migrating](#) subjects.

- Authentication effects -

EcoPart unauthenticated user : can only view samples on map and compute stats on project (regardless of the project status)

EcoPart authenticated user : can at least export public projects

EcoTaxa unauthenticated user : If an EcoTaxa project is linked to the EcoPart project and if the EcoPart user is manager or member, the user will be able to export zoo data from EcoTaxa through EcoPart. Users will not be able to create and/or link an EcoTaxa project through the EcoPart project creation step.

EcoTaxa authenticated user : Users will be able to create and/or link an EcoTaxa project through the EcoPart project creation step.

The **UVPdb** app will need to provide an API endpoint to fetch inter-calibrations (no authentication needed).

Private project :

	See the project	Stats on project	Generate figures	Export particles data	Export EcoTaxa classification data	Import samples	Manage project
Anonym	V	V	X	X	X	X	X
User	V	V	X	X	X	X	X
Member	V	V	V	V	V	V	X
Manager	V	V	V	V	V	V	V

Visible project :

	See the project	Stats on project	Generate figures	Export particles data	Import samples	Export EcoTaxa classification data	Manage project
Anonym	V	V	X	X	X	X	X
User	V	V	V	X	X	X	X
Member	V	V	V	V	V	V	X
Manager	V	V	V	V	V	V	V

Public project :

	See the project	Stats on project	Generate figures	Export particles data	Export EcoTaxa classification data	Import samples	Manage project
Anonym	V	V	V	X	X	X	X
User	V	V	V	V	X	X	X
Member	V	V	V	V	V	V	X
Manager	V	V	V	V	V	V	V

Public+ project :

	See the project	Stats on project	Generate figures	Export particles data	Export EcoTaxa classification data	Import samples	Manage project
Anonym	V	V	V	X	X	X	X
User	V	V	V	V	V	X	X
Member	V	V	V	V	V	V	X
Manager	V	V	V	V	V	V	V

9. API

a. Formalism

Communication between EcoPart backend and the front or a third party app (such as code base data consumer) will only take place through Backend api endpoints calls.

We are going to follow the **REST API** formalism.

We will allow **CRUD** (Create, Read, Update, Delete) actions on resources and use following verbs :

POST	:	Create new resource
GET	:	Read existing resource
PUT	:	Update by replacing entire existing resource
DELETE	:	Delete the resource
PATCH	:	Update only the specifying part of the existing resource

Prefer **idempotent** operation for API endpoints. In our context idempotent means that the API endpoint can be applied multiple times without changing the result beyond the initial call.

We will use :

- Caching (mostly on get endpoints)
- JSON data transfer
- Status codes
- URI hierarchy
- Idempotent or safe HTTP methods
- Implement security

Our URI will be constructed using only **lowercase**, and [kebab-case](#).

We will not use any verb.

REST URI best practices :

- “ / ” indicates hierarchy
- Use plural nouns for branches
- Hyphens for multiples words

- Use lowercase
- Refrain to using file extensions
- Do not use action verbs

Returns status codes will be return depending of the status of the emitted request :

- 200 : success
- 400 : client side error
- 500 : server side error

b. Specification

Here is a first version of the API specification : [API-ECOPART-V0](#)

10. Project

General

A project can be created by any authenticated EcoPart user, it can then be edited by its managers. A project can also be deleted.

In the “list project” page, we only want to show projects where the logged user has a member or manage privilege. The search for a project and request access will take place in the explore part.

When the user loads the metadata from the root folder, and the metadata contains emails related to existing EcoPart user email accounts, it will automatically fill up the privilege part with their accounts as members.

Example of loaded project peoples metadata. In this example we can see that Lars does not have an existing account unlike Marc and Eric :

Root folder path*
plankton/uyv5_missions/uyv5_sn000_tara2011 [Load metadata](#)

Project peoples

Data owner name* Lars Stemmann	Data owner email* lars.stemmann@obs-vlfr.fr
Operator name* Marc Picheral	Operator email* marc.picheral@obs-vlfr.fr
Chief scientist name* Eric Karsenti	Chief scientist email* karsenti@embl.de

A manager can see all the tasks that concern the project in the Tasks tab.

Remote instrument

If the used instrument contains “remote” then

- the “host name” section will be displayed. We want to allow the user to set up at creation or lately a remote repository where retrieve data.

- The creation of an EcoTaxa project is disabled. In case a remote instrument is recovered and raw data downloaded, it becomes a regular instrument. As so, a new EcoPart and EcoTaxa project are created to host the downloaded data and the remote project can be either kept or deleted.

Project creation in EcoTaxa from EcoPart

Create a project in EcoTaxa will require :

- Connected EcoTaxa user.

The project created will be empty.

The Project instrument will depends on the EcoPart selected instrument as follow

EcoPart	EcoTaxa
UVP5HD	UVP5HD
UVP5SD	UVP5SD
UVP5Z	UVP5Z
UVP6	UVP6
UVP6_REMOTE	NO ECOAXA PROJECT CREATION
UVP6M	UVP6
UVP6M_REMOTE	NO ECOAXA PROJECT CREATION

We will call the following EcoTaxa API endpoint with the related User Token :

https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/api/docs#/projects/create_project

```
{
  "title": "My new project title",
  "instrument": "UVP5",
  "visible": true
}
```

Project metadata :

Attr name	Type	Mand	Editable	Default	Description	Will loading data from the project root path fill this attr? If yes, from?
Project id	Number	Y	N	/	Generated sequential number following the previous project id.	/

Project title	String	Y	Y	/	The title of the EcoPart project.	Root folder name
EcoTaxa Project	Number	N	Y	/	[Create_a_new_EcoTaxa_project_with_same_title() OR liknke_an_existing_EcoTaxa_project()] in both cases should be logged to EcoTaxa, in the second, should be the manager of the EcoTaxa project. “Associated project where you will import the images from the « work » folders. You can create a new associated project here.”	/
EcoTaxa Account	EcoTaxaAccount object	N	Y	/	Linked user account to an EcoTaxa instance	/
Data owner name	String	Y	Y	/	Data Owner is also the Contact : can be the manager, no login requested NB : a Contact needs to be set, it will be the data owner, it has no impact on access control or privacy of the project.	/config/cruise_info.txt -> do_name
Data owner email	String	Y	Y	/		/config/cruise_info.txt -> do_email
Instrument	String	Y	N	/	“Selected from the root folder name MUST BE : UVP5HD UVP5SD UVP5Z UVP6 UVP6_REMOTE UVP6M UVP6M_REMOTE	Part before first “_” in root folder name (no distinction between uvp6 hf et lp) SN uvp5>=200 : HD else SD UVP5ZD UVP5ZH (! SN before)
Instrument sérial number	String	Y	N	/	Serial number	Part between first and second “_” in Root folder name
Operator name	String	Y	Y	/	People who managed the acquisition of the data.	/config/cruise_info.txt -> op_name
Operator email	String	Y	Y	/		/config/cruise_info.txt -> op_email
Chief scientist name	String	Y	Y	/	People who conducted the cruise.	/config/cruise_info.txt -> cs_name
Chief scientist email	String	Y	Y	/		/config/cruise_info.txt -> cs_email
Project	String	N	Y	/	“free field (e.g., as filled in the	/config/cruise_info.txt

acronym					cruise_info.txt file)"	-> acron
Override depth offset	Float	N	Y	UVP5 : 1.2	<p>The depth offset is the vertical distance between the pressure sensor and the imaged zone (positive if pressure sensor above imaged area). This information can be filled in the project metadata page for the entire project or at sample level.</p> <p>In case the project depth offset is documented, it will override the sample depth offsets for the process of the project.</p> <p>The project depth offset is automatically set to 1.2 if your instrument is UVP5 during read project metadata operation as the sample depth offsets are not documented in the instrument metadata.</p> <p>The sample depth offsets are set in the instrument metadata for the UVP6 instrument and automatically documented in EcoPart for each sample.</p>	UVP5 : non documenté
Cruise /WMO	String	Y	Y	/	The cruise's name.	/meta/rootfoldername.txt -> cruise
Ship /floatref	[String]	Y	Y	/	The ship's name.	/meta/rootfoldername.txt -> ship
Enable descent filter	Bool	Y	Y	True for UVP5 and the False for UVP6	<p>The Descent filter operates during the import of the samples. It checks the pressure and removes images acquired when UVP is ascending. The filter applies only on UVP data (UVP6remote excluded). NO : no filtering in any case YES : applied on 'depth' samples of the project EMPTY : automatically applies the 'YES' rule for UVP5 and the 'NO' rule for UVP6</p>	/
Project information	String	N	Y	/	"read from the cruise_info.txt file"	/config/cruise_info.txt ->gen_info
Creation date	Date	Y	N	/	The date of creation of the project	/
Filtered project	Bool	Y	Y	False	If data where filtered before import in EcoPart	!

Time duration check	Bool	Y	Y	True	Disable if the project is longer than 1 year.	/
---------------------	------	---	---	------	---	---

Project privacy :

The start date of the delay is the date of the older sample of the project.

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description
Project privacy status	Enum[string]	Y	Y	Private	Private, Visible, Public, Public+
Privacy delay	Number in month	Y	Y	2 months after today	Delay until project status became visible
General download delay	Number in month	Y	Y	24 months after today	Delay until project status became public
EcoTaxa classification download delay	Number in month	Y	Y	36 months after today	Delay until project status became public+

La licence du projet ecotaxa sera piloté par ecopart "EcoTaxa classification download delay".

Project roles :

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description
Managers	[Users]	Y(one at least)	Y	Current user	Name of one or more managers of the project, to be selected in the EcoPart user list. The project manager will manage the project (import/export / edit metadata/ manage privilege ...)
Members	[Users]	N	Y	/	Bypass the privacy deadlines (view figures, stats on the project, export particles data, export EcoTaxa classification data)

Project data : It does depend on instrument type (remote or not).

- **Root folder (NOT REMOTE):**

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description
Local dir	String	N	Y	/	Path to project folder. "SELECT the UVP root folder from the drive (request FTP permission from the

					application manager to load your projects or load data from a local drive). Press "Read Metadata" button to read the « cruise_info.txt » file again”
--	--	--	--	--	--

- **Connexion to data server (REMOTE):**

If the option is activated, remote UVP6 data will be automatically pulled and imported once per day. The user can force the import of new samples from the "IMPORT" menu in his project.

To stop the automatic pooling when the remote data acquisition ends, the user will be able to disable the automatic sync.

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description
Remote type	Enum[string]	N	Y	/	ARGO or TSV LOV
Host	String	N	Y	/	Hostname/IP @ of remote server for FTP URL for http & https
Directory on server	String	N	Y	/	directory on remote server with / as separator
User	String	N	Y	/	
Password	String	N	Y	/	
Additional reference of the vector	String	N	Y	/	This reference can help searching in associated databases. It can be the serial number of the glider, the IMO number of the ARGO float
Automatic synchronization	Bool	Y	N	/	When activated, pull data once per day.

Project stats

The project stats will show stats to the user for the given project :

First a block containing some general stats :

Number of stations,

number of samples,

approximate number of particles,

number of vignettes

and the number of both total or partial exports.

Then a date privacy status with all dates of data privacy gates.

Then the map of samples and CTD data will be displayed.

Then a block containing the number of depth profile,
the number of time profile,
and a total.

Then a block containing a maximum pressure bar plot by samples, with range 0-500,
500-1000, 1000-2000, 2000-3000 named : pressure slices [db] (in decibar)

Then a bloc containing stats about ranges :

- Pressure range
- Size range
- Time range

Then a block containing all categories from EcoTaxa classification.

Then a block containing some EcoTaxa classification state like :

the percentage of validated object,
the percentage of predicted object,
the percentage of validated object,
the percentage of Samples fully predicted,
the percentage of Samples fully validated,
the percentage of Samples partially predicted,
the percentage of Samples partially validated.

Over the stats will be a layer of intelligence thanks to quality checks and associated actions (advice about action like “we detect a possible QC error on your data, please run ootb solution or modify values... ”) :

- Mismatch instruments specifications
- link missing CTD sample
- Import samples (empty project)
- Link an EcoTaxa project

- Link to classify in EcoTaxa
- GPS checks for samples

To see detailed specifications on these availables QC please go to the QC chapter.

11. Sample

Actions allowed on a sample at the sample page level: delete and edit.

Samples of a project need to be accessible in a dedicated page.

Currently the following information are available :

PARTICLE informations

Part. project ID * : 555

CTD filename (import) : tara_sbe_9c_110311_01

Taxonomy QC :

Profile ID * : tara_093_00_a

CTD name (import) : Julie Coustenoble

Particles QC :

EcoTaxa SampleID :

CTD email (import) : julie.coustenoble@imev-mer.fr

CTD status :

Filename * : 20110311194210

CTD date & time (import) : 2022-12-05 15:14:44

CTD desc :

01=Angular scattering coef at 117° 470 nm [m-1 Sr-1]

02=Bbp470 [m-1]

03=Beam Transmission 660 nm [%]

04=Beam attenuation coef 660 nm [m-1]

05=Nitrate ISUS [µMol/L]

06=Oxygen [ml/l]

07=Oxygen [umol/Kg]

08=Oxygen Per Sat [µmol/Kg]

09=PAR ratio [%]

10=Part backscattering coef 470 nm [m-1]

11=Ph

12=Time [second]

Profile METADATA

Instrument SN :
Station ID : tara_093_00_a
Barcode :
Wind direction [°] (0-360) : 270
Profile UTC date & time : 2011-03-11 19:42:10
Latitude [DD.DDDD] (- for South) : -33.45717
First image Ok : 407
Wind speed [knots] : 10
Operator name :
Longitude [DDD.DDDD] (- for West) : -72.15433
Last img Ok : 9999999999
Sea state (1-12) : 3
Operator email :
Bottom depth [m] : 133
Last image utilized : 4108
Nebuloussness (0-8) : 1
Profile Type : Depth
Descent filtered row : 74
Removed empty slice :
Integration time (Time profile) [s] :
Comment : no

Instrument

Instrument SN :
Aa (for UVP6, value is divided by 106) : 0.016637
Exp : 1.1241
Image Volume [L] : 1.03
Acq Ratio : 3
Process datetime :
Acq Shutter speed : 12
Acq Xsize : 1280
Process gamma
Acq Exposure :
Acq Ysize : 960

Images post process :
 Zooprocess :
 Pixel size [mm] : 0.174
 Acq Gain : 6
 Acq Erase border (0/1) :
 Process ratio :
 Depth Offset [M] :
 Acq Description :
 Acq Threshold : 5
 Particle minimum size [pixels] : 1
 Acq Task type : 2
 Vignettes minimum size [Pixels] : 30
 Acq Choice : 1
 Presure gain :
 Acq Disk type : 0
 Acq descent filter : yes

The following information will be available in the new version of EcoPart :

Profile ID : The EcoPart sample ID. Example : “tara_093_00_a”

Context

General

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
EcoPart project ID	Number	Y	N	/	The related EcoPart project id
EcoPart project name	String	Y	N	/	The related EcoPart project
File name	String	N	Y	/	The referenced file name in metadata. Exemple : 20110311194210

EcoTaxa

Possibility open link and view in EcoTaxa

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
EcoTaxa project ID	Number	N	N	/	The related EcoTaxa project id, if imported in EcoTaxa.
EcoTaxa project name	String	N	N	/	The related EcoTaxa project name, if imported in EcoTaxa.
EcoTaxa SampleID	Number	N	N	/	The related EcoTaxa sample id, if imported in EcoTaxa.

CTD

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Original file name	String	Y	N	/	The original CTD file name referenced in metadata, can be seabird .cnv but not only! Example : tara_sbe_9c_110311_01
Imported file name	String	Y	N	/	The effective imported CTD file name Example : tara_sbe_9c_110311_01.ctd
Importator name	String	Y	N	/	The name of the user that runs the import within that sample. Example : Julie Coustenoble
Importator email	String	Y	N	/	The email of the user that runs the import within that sample. Example : julie.coustenoble@imev-mer.fr
Import date	UTC date time	Y	N	/	Import date in UTC format
Imported CTD description	LONG String	N	N	/	Imported CTD description Example : 01=Angular scattering coef at 117° 470 nm [m-1 Sr-1] 02=Bbp470 [m-1] 03=Beam Transmission 660 nm [%] 04=Beam attenuation coef 660 nm [m-1] 05=Nitrate ISUS [µMol/L] 06=Oxygen [ml/l] 07=Oxygen [umol/Kg] 08=Oxygen Per Sat [µmol/Kg] 09=PAR ratio [%]

					10=Part backscattering coef 470 nm [m-1] 11=Ph 12=Time [second]
--	--	--	--	--	---

Metadata

Sample

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Sample ID	String	Y	N	/	
Type	Enum(depth/time)	Y	Y	/	
UTC date & time	UTC date time	Y	Y	/	
Instrument serial number	String	Y	N	/	
Max pressure	In decibar	Y	Y	/	
Comment	String	N	Y	/	
Optional id (ARGO, Glider)	String	N	Y	/	
Integration time (Time profile) [s]	In second	N	Y	/	If the sample type is time only!

Station

If a CTD file with valid latitude/longitude is imported, the user can choose to use local or imported CTD coordinates for his sample.

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Station ID	String	Y	N	/	
Sampling date	UTC date time	Y	Y	/	
Local Latitude	Relative float Decimal deg [DD.DDDD]	Y	Y	/	Latitude from local imported data (- for South)
Local Longitude	Relative float Decimal deg [DD.DDDD]	Y	Y	/	longitude from local imported data (- for West)
Imported CTD Latitude	Relative float Decimal deg [DD.DDDD]	N	N	/	If CTD file is imported, latitude from the imported CTD file (- for South)
Imported CTD Longitude	Relative float Decimal deg	N	N	/	If CTD file is imported, longitude from the imported CTD file

	[DD.DDDD]				(- for West)
--	-----------	--	--	--	--------------

Environment

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Wind direction (0-360)	Number (0-360) in Deg	N	Y	/	
Sea state (1-12)	Int (1-12)	N	Y	/	
Bottom depth	Number in meter	N	Y	/	
Wind speed	Number in knots	N	Y	/	
Nebulosity (0-8)	Number (0-8)	N	Y	/	

Operator

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Name	String	N	Y	/	
Email	String	N	Y	/	

Instrument

Instrument SN : 000001LP

Calibration details (recommended and local)

Recommended :

These parameters are pulled from From UvpDB, for the given period, serial number and key image acquisition parameters, in the UI a link to the UVPDB calibration page will be available.

If nothing match in UVPDB, so we will show to the user the following message with a link to uvpDB :

“NO MATCHING CALIBRATION DETAILS IN UvpDB

for the given period, serial number and key image acquisition parameters ”

UVP DB needs to offer an API to do so.

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Aa	String	Y	N	/	(for UVP6, value is divided by 106)
Exp	String	Y	N	/	
Image Volume	Number [L]	Y	N	/	
Pixel size	Number [mm]	Y	N	/	

Local :

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Aa	String	Y	Y	/	(for UVP6, value is divided by 106)
Exp	String	Y	Y	/	
Image Volume	Number [L]	Y	Y	/	
Pixel size	Number [mm]	Y	Y	/	

Key acquisition parameters :

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Shutter speed	Number	Y	Y	/	
Gain	Number	Y	Y	/	
Transfert	Number	Y	Y	/	
Threshold	Number	Y	Y	/	

Other acquisition parameters

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Exposure	Number			/	
Erase border (0/1)	Bool			/	
Description	String			/	
Task type	Number			/	
Choice	Number				
Disk type	Number				
Ratio	Number				

Enabled descendent filter	Bool				
X size	Number				
Y size	Number				
Particle minimum size	Number [pixels]				
Vignette minimum size	Number [pixels]				
Pressure gain	Number				For now is a conversion factor because for uvp5 centibar decibar to convert in decimetre... But we need to remove it and only show the correct value of gain.
Depth offset	Number [M]				

Process details

Attr name	Type	Mandatory	Editable	Default	Description or example
Image post process	String	Y	Y	/	UVPAPP, Zooprocess
UTC date time	UTC date time	Y	Y	/	
Ratio	Number	Y	Y	/	
Process gamma	Number	Y	Y	/	

Quality check

Three kind of QC will be shown :

- Particles QC
- Station QC
- Taxonomy QC

They will be detailed in the following QC chapter.

12. Import

General

The import will be available for : Manager and members.

The types instruments data we want to import are :

- UVP5 (filtered or not)
- UVP6 : brut (Output of the UVP app) :
 - time
 - depth
 - slant (glider) (we do it by keeping track of depth by time in CTD file, but we don't exploit it)

→ Notion of "black" in the middle of other images (0:1) No light images to quantify the noise.

- UVP6 remote : 2 supported format :
 - NetCDF (.nc) => Argo data
 - Tsv table + meta
- CTD : CTD files import, the boat trajectory is associated to CTD data in file context, need to choose a more generic extension.

List of supported instruments data import :

- UVP5HD
- UVP5SD
- UVP5Z
- UVP6LP
- UVP6HF
- UVP6_REMOTE
- UVP6M
- UVP6M_REMOTE
- CTD (.ctd, and .cnv but not a priority)

For UVP6 and different models of uvp5 here are the desired datasource :

 UVP data sources for import

Here are some existing EcoPart projects that represent almost all the existing cases

:

UVP5

model	Ecopart project	path	CTD
UVP5HD	uvp5_sn205_perle_03_2020 (238)	uvp5_sn205_perle_03_2020	no CTD
UVP5SD	uvp5_sn003_ccelter_2016 (43)	uvp5_sn003_ccelter_2016	CTD sans LAT/LON
UVP5Z	uvp5_sn002zd_omer_2 (38)	uvp5_sn002zd_omer_2	CTD sans LAT/LON

UVP6 :

model	Ecopart project	path	CTD
UVP6LP TIME	uvp6_sn000002lp_201909_m158 (411)	uvp6_sn000002lp\uvp6_sn000002lp_201909_m158	
UVP6 AUTO	uvp6_sn000008lp_20220610_intercalibrage (532)	_UVP6_projets_intercalibrage\000008LP\2022\uvp6_sn000008lp_20220610_intercalibrage	no CTD
UVP6HF CTD	uvp6_sn000125hf_202205_talpro (524)	uvp6_sn000125hf\uvp6_sn000125hf_202205_talpro	no CTD
UVP6LP AUTO	uvp6_sn000005lp_20220610_intercalibrage (531)	_UVP6_projets_intercalibrage\000005LP\2022\uvp6_sn000005lp_20220610_intercalibrage	no CTD
UVP6_REMO TE	uvp6_sn000101lp_2020_float_triatlas_remote (356)		

UVP6 SUPERVISED	uvp6_sn000110lp_2021_WMO6904139_recovery (605)	uvp6_sn000110lp\uvp6_sn000110lp_2021_WMO6904139_recovery	CTD avec LAT/LON
UVP6 HF TIME		uvp6_sn000171hf\uvp6_sn000171hf_20230720_wcb_1	No CTD

UVP6m :

UVP6M : Waiting : provide UVP6M format data folder to import

UVP6M_REMOTE : Waiting : provide NetCDF (.nc) file

Import Particles (LPM)

The import can be manual or remote, it depends on the instrument used (remote or not).

In the manual case the system, based on the root folder, local or on a remote server, will show to the user new samples available to import, it will also list and show samples already imported to update, the system will finally provide a feature to update only metadata. The user will be able to delete samples, this action will cause deletion of the CTD associated sample and will automatically flag related vignettes in EcoTaxa to a deprecated status (tag=2).

In a second time we could consider adding an ftp access directly on EcoPart as in EcoTaxa. (as with pyftplib)

Import in EcoTaxa

EcoPart application will provide two different features in the UI : import new samples and open already imported samples in EcoTaxa. The user will need to be logged to his EcoTaxa account from EcoPart and needs Imports permission on the target project.

These actions will be performed by API call to the two following endpoint :

https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/api/docs#/projects/import_file

https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/api/docs#/projects/simple_import

And : the project URL page with selected samples id as filters.

When a sample is deleted from EcoTaxa, it will appear in EcoPart as a new sample to import in EcoTaxa.

Import from EcoPart to EcoTaxa action is always manual.

Import CTD samples

EcoPart application will provide different features to import, update and delete CTD samples. CTD samples can be imported for all the supported instruments. The supported formats will be “.ctd”, and “.cnv” but not a priority.

CTD files will allow the import of LAT/LON data by pressure for oblique profiles, as for glider datasets.

13. L0-b backup

Backup raw at the project level

- Available for : Manager and members.
- This action will trigger a task
- Allow to backup L0-b level of data.
- It will not depend on what samples are imported in the application, it will just backup the whole raw project as it is.
- files that will be copied are the following :
 - UVP6 : raw/*, meta/*, and config/*.
 - UVP5 : raw/*, meta/*, and config/*.
 - Raw sub-folders will be zipped (and compressed)
- It will only be available by project.
- "skip already imported" option is available and allow the user to import only the new data from the raw folder without overwriting what's already imported. And with updating meta/* and config/*.
- Else everything is imported (overwrite backed samples)
- At a new backup, missing raw data is not deleted.
- at every new backup meta and config will be overwritten
- In the UI add a warning if no backup L0-b
- For each import/import update, we trigger an L0-b backup with (an option in import/import update entry points that launches the backup task with "Skip already imported").

Export backed-up raw data by project

- Available for : Manager and members.
- The option out_to_ftp : In addition to a direct download link available in the task, your export will be located on the FTP in the folder:
ecopart_exported_data/task_id/ecopart_backup_export_projid_YYYYMMDD_HHMMSS.zip.
- This action will trigger a task
- Allow to export backup L0-b level of data.
- it will not depend on what samples are imported in the application, it will just export the whole backed-up L0-b project as it is.

14. QC

Quality checks will take place at three different levels in the app :

- Import time level
- Project stats level
- Sample info level

At the **import time level** we will show three types of graphs for each sample, the user will have to validate the quality of it to complete the import. Here are the three types of graphs :

The first graph will be “Vertical profile of the pressure of each image”. With related images selection info :

The second graph will be “Vertical profile of imaged volume versus pressure”.

The last set of graphs will be :

- “Vertical profile of black for 1, 2 and 3 pixels versus pressure .”
- “Vertical profile of particle (LPM) for 1, 2 and 3 pixels versus pressure.”

(maybe in simlog : to determine regarding data shape)

Vertical profile of black for 1, 2 and 3 pixels versus pressure.

Vertical profile of particle (LPM) for 1, 2 and 3 pixels versus pressure.

In a second time, these graphs will be available at **sample level**.

The sample QC tab will contain three QC level :

- Particles (previous QC graphs with validated by & datetime of validation)
- Station (gps coordinates of samples and gps coordinates of CTD on a map)
- Taxonomic (the classification percentage of the sample, validated and predicted)

Eventually at the **project stat level** will be multiple pseudo QC in order to help the user to own a complete and reliable project.

QC	CTA	Action
If empty project	Your project is empty ! Please import data.	Link to “import” tab of the project
If no project linked	Your project isn’t linked to an EcoTaxa project ! Please link it to an existing or new EcoTaxa project.	Link to tab metadata section “Link to EcoTaxa”

If project linked and samples to import	3 samples not imported in EcoTaxa	Link to "import" tab of the project
If data not totally annotate in EcoTaxa project	classification uncompleted	Link to EcoTaxa with related filters to select samples to annotate.
If the size of the object mismatch the instrument range	mismatch instrument specification	Open objects in ecotaxa (if applicable) or Link to list of imported samples containing the suspicious value
If samples without CTD	missing 1 CTd file	Link to "import" tab of the project
If samples gps coordinates mismatch CTD coordinates	Mismatch 1 sample gps coordinates	Link to sample coordinate
If the time range of samples in the project are more than one year or sample data is before 2008	Suspicious time range	Link to data tab, where user can see date by samples
If the pressure of a sample is < -5db or >11000	Suspicious pressure	Link to data tab, where user can see date by samples, RAW data will be corrected "manually" by the data importer
If instrum == uvp5hd and filtered == false	Unfiltered uvp5hd project Some UVP5HD require filtering of the projects they produce, if this is not the case for your project you can disable the option here	Link to this QC option in the metadata tab in the project. This QC option can be disabled.
Time duration check	Suspicious time range	Link to list of imported samples containing the suspicious time range sample, this QC option can be disabled.

Other data quality controls were considered as follow, in orange what we decide to don't do :

(Existing requirements : <https://app.clickup.com/t/1ej4dbg>)

- **Cross check of position and datetime data against GPS positions from CTD, Ships stationbook, ships cruistrack record (** <https://app.clickup.com/t/1equ05t>)
- **Check position data for outliers on land (redundant with cross check against ships stationbook)**, Needs a map and a final manual expertise as the coastlines are not always perfect (problem of melting coastal glaciers...)
- **Check that the DateTime of the first and last profile are within the cruise period of time.** (Could you be more explicit ? These date-time info are automatically labelled by the instruments... if their datetime is well set ! Yepp, and the automatic labelling of the datetime can be checked against CTD and cruise log data. We had issues before that the clock of the UVP5 was reset e.g. to 1986, so the HDR filename and everything might be wrong. **As mentioned, this is redundant with against a check against the stationbook, but if that does not exist**, the user should somehow provide a start and end date of the cruise to at least find the most obvious errors. => *we will do a time duration check cf table above*

Crucial: Check format of ctd_filename info (needs to coincide with actual format, should not be e.g. 1.ctd, 2.ctd ...), The CTD data QC and management will remain out of the scope of this tool. The problem of the CTD file naming is a field problem (operator to fill in the metadata) or a Data management issue (the scientist or data manager working for him has to prepare the CTD data for importation and check their association with the UVP data).

- **Check aa, exp, observed volume in UVP5 metadata against calibration data sheet**, Calibration and related instrument settings must be read from the UVPdb web app.
- **Check that UVP5 HD data have been corrected for lights (if necessary)**
- **Check particle size distribution for outliers, @Rainer Kiko Please provide a spec. otherwise impossible !**

- Check that pressure of UVP coincides with external info (surface rinsing should be at 1 dbar, bottom pressure against ctd data). If necessary, correct pressure info, Problem in project 125hf fjords!!!

<https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4515>

Negative pressure values found, although instrument was in water. This means that the entire profile is offset, in comparison to e.g. CTD data etc.

also for 126hf in this project : <https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/5228>

The UVP6 pressure 600 bars sensor is of top quality but its absolute accuracy is "only" 0.1% full scale (ie 6m). You cannot thus only apply an offset from a surface pressure measurement only.

My opinion is that the "correction" of the UVP measurements must be done by the scientist using the data according to their requested precision and methods.

This is a hardware / software failure of the instrument... Measurements are 10dbar off, so more than the precision. => *we will do a pressure check : "If the pressure of a sample is < -5db or >11000" cf table above.*

15. Explore

Select sample depending of :

A list of project

Instrument

Location (North, South, East, West)

Date (duration from date to date or a selection of months) : samples will be selected if it is at least partially included in the periode.

Time

Pressure in decibar db (All samples that encompass the selected range)

Sample type

Status : Private, Visible, Public, Public+, My projects (override the status and gives total access to data to the current user)

CTD : Sample linked to CTD data (yes or no)

EcoTaxa : Sample imported in EcoTaxa

Classification state : Fully predicted, fully validated

Available actions :

- Stats
- Graphs
- Share graph
- Facilitating the project search and the process of adding to the project
- Export

Two tabs will be available.

In the first one named “**Selected data stats**” :

- A map able to switch from polar to regular display. It will show selected samples depending on selected filters.
- A table of with at least one sample in the selection
- Multiples graphs like : Sample count per instruments, time distribution, max pressure
- Multiples Ranges : Pressure range, time range, size range
- Info about samples type (depth or time)
- List of EcoTaxa classifications

- EcoTaxa classification state (fully or partially validated or predicted)
- 4 random images from selected samples from EcoTaxa

In the second one named “**Selected data graphs**” :

- A block able to display **LPM abundance** related graphs.
- A block able to display **LPM biovolume** related graphs.
- A block able to display **CTD data** related graphs.
- A block able to display **EcoTaxa classification** related graphs.

For each block user will be able to select :

- class size :

	BLACK	1 pixel	2 pixels									
UVP5SD		X	X	50.8	64	80.6	128	256	512	1020	2050	4100
UVP5HD		X	X	50.8	64	80.6	128	256	512	1020	2050	4100
UVP5Z		X	X	50.8	64	80.6	128	256	512	1020	2050	4100
UVP6 (LP et HF)	X	X	X	50.8	64	80.6	128	256	512	1020	2050	4100
UVP6_remote	X	X	X	50.8	64	80.6	128	256	512	1020	2050	4100
UVP6M	?	X	X									
UVP6M (LP et HF)	?	X	X									

OR CTD parameter

(chloro fluo [mg chl m-3] conductivity [ms cm-1] cpar [%] depth [m] fcdom [ppb qse] in situ density anomaly [kg m-3] nitrate [umol l-1] oxygen [umol kg-1] oxygen [ml l-1] par [umol m-2 s-1] potential density anomaly [kg m-3] potential temperature [degc] practical salinity [psu] pressure [db] spar [umol m-2 s-1] temperature [degc] time [yyyymmddhhmmssmmm]),

OR EcoTaxa classification taxon

- DATA Scale (Linear - Log - Symlog)
- TIME Scale (Relative or Absolute),

Relative time scale : put each beginning of project at the same time (0) and the scale is now representative of elapse time.

Absolute time scale : on a true date time scale

- The user will also be able to adjust the time and pressure min and max for display graphs.

For the legend, if multiples project : by project. If only one project, by samples and no global legend. Make the data traceable (show from which project and/or sample the line come from).

Particle profile for some large classes: moving average.

For the EcoTaxa classification part, users will be able to select childrens of a taxon. If multiple projects sum by project.

Technically we will use the object EcoTaxa API endpoint to get data and construct graphs.

16. Export

The user will be able to export data related to the selection he did in the Explore page.

Two export types will be available, each export will contain a summary table.

Current available informations for the summary of **detailed** export format

profile	Cruise	Site	DataOwner	Rawfilename	Instrument	CTDrosettefilename	yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm	Latitude	Longitude	aa	exp	Pixel size	Particle filename	Plankton filename	Project
at38s1_5c1	sn201_2017_naames_03	S1-5	lee karp boss(lee.karp-boss@marine.edu)	HDR20170905153339	uvp5	at38s1-5c1	2017-09-05 15:33:39	43.7148	-42.90123	0.0036191	1.1154	0.086	export_detailed_20230210_10_59_PAR_at38s1_5c1.tsv	export_detailed_20230210_10_59_ZOO_at38s1_5c1.tsv	uvp5_sn201_2017_naames_03

Current available informations for the summary of **raw** export format :

psampleid	16193
pprojid	92
profileid	at38s1_5c1
filename	20170905153339
sampleid	47774
latitude	43.7148
longitude	-42.90123
organizedbydepth	True
histobrutavailable	True
qualitytaxo	
qualitypart	
daterecalculhistotaxo	2021-04-08 06:50:52.609538
winddir	99
winspeed	99
seastate	2
nebuloussness	99
comment	no
stationid	S1-5
firstimage	4151
lastimg	99999999
lastimgused	35981
bottomdepth	480
yoyo	False

sampledate	2017-09-05 15:33:39
op_sample_name	
op_sample_email	
ctd_desc	01=Angular scattering coef at 117° 470 nm [m-1 Sr-1] \$02=Bbp470 [m-1] \$03=Beam Transmission 660 nm [%] \$04=Beam attenuation coef 660 nm [m-1] \$05=Oxygen [ml/l] \$06=Oxygen Per Sat [µmol/Kg] \$07=PAR ratio [%] \$08=Part backscattering coef 470 nm [m-1] \$09=Ph \$10=Time [second]
ctd_origfilename	at38s1-5c1
ctd_import_name	Marc Picheral
ctd_import_email	mp@gmail.com
ctd_import_datetime	2020-07-08 16:06:47.112300
ctd_status	
instrumsn	sn201
acq_aa	0.00266
acq_exp	1.2194
acq_volimage	1.13
acq_depthoffset	
acq_pixel	0.094
acq_shutterspeed	
acq_smzoo	80
acq_exposure	160
acq_gain	200
acq_filedescription	uvp5hd sn201 : mixtfd
acq_eraseborder	0
acq_tasktype	2
acq_threshold	3
acq_choice	0
acq_disktype	0
acq_smbase	1
acq_ratio	3
acq_descent_filter	True
acq_presure_gain	
acq_xsize	2048
acq_ysize	2048
acq_barcode	
proc_datetime	
proc_gamma	
proc_soft	Zooprocess
lisst_zscat_filename	
lisst_kernel	
txt_data01	

txt_data02	
txt_data03	
txt_data04	
txt_data05	
txt_data06	
txt_data07	
txt_data08	
txt_data09	
txt_data10	
ptitle	uvp5_sn201_2017_naames_03
rawfolder	local_plankton/uvp/uvp_b/uvp5_sn201_2017_naames_03
ownerid	Nils Haentjens (nils.haentjens@maine.edu)
projid	637
instrumtype	UVP5
op_name	emmanuel boss
op_email	emmanuel.boss@maine.edu
cs_name	mike behrenfeld
cs_email	mjb@science.oregonstate.edu
do_name	lee karp boss
do_email	lee.karp-boss@maine.edu
prj_info	
prj_acronym	naames 03
cruise	sn201_2017_naames_03
ship	atlantis
default_instrumsn	sn201
default_depthoffset	default_depthoffset
Particle filename	20180330053614_s3c1_PAR_raw_20230210_11_02.tsv
CTD filename	20180330053614_s3c1_CTD_raw_20230210_11_02.tsv
Plankton filename	20180330053614_s3c1_ZOO_raw_20230210_11_02.tsv

Format we want now for the summary : [Summary](#)

A file at project level : Projects

A file at sample level : Samples

 RAW data (filter granularity : **sample**)

As we don't ensure the backup, we don't export the whole raw folder.

Following options will be available :

Select what you want to export : LPM, EcoTaxa classification and CTD. The summary will be exported by default.

- **Summary :**

Homogenous between both exports.

Format by sample with info on project, data owner et operators, lat, lon, bottom depth... See example above.

- **LPM:**

UVP5 : Dat, bru and meta for uvp5 + UVP6 format

UVP6 : Format uvp6. One row per image

One row by image : UVP data formatting, compute at import for UVP5

Meta (header) to edit to add the units for example

In the case of uvp6 remote (ARGO) netcdf : uvp6 remote format already binned

- **EcoTaxa classification :**

TSV format (without histogram) 1 line per object

Corresponds to a default export in EcoTaxa

In case of multiple projects, we will do one call to the EcoTaxa API per project.

Do we want to get images from EcoTaxa ? : NO.

Custom export, no images, split by sample to be consistent with LPM

- **CTD** : as imported

Binned data (granularité des filtres **objet**)

Following options will be available :

Select what you want to export : LPM, EcoTaxa classification and CTD. The summary will be exported by default.

- **Summary :**

Homogenous between both exports.

Format by sample with info on project, data owner et operators, lat, lon, bottom depth... See example above.

- **LPM(size spectra) :**

Choice of bins (time/depth) directly in the explore page, but can be overwritten in the export page.

Also choice of size classes by instrument listed here:

 [EcoPART_size_classes.xlsx](#)

The output file will contain the useful size class columns only, if a count is 0, put 0. If there is no value for an instrument, put NA (according to the smallest size class visible by the instrument concerned). It will make the following operations easier for the data consumer.

As ODV users told us that flexibility of the accepted format in terms of row/column organisation in ODV software is limited, we choose to propose two export format one ODV and one TSV with the same info but organised differently.

Users can export in TSV format (optimised for code base utilisation) or ODV format (optimised for Ocean Data View ootb based utilisation).

In the case of uvp6 remote (ARGO) netcdf : bin argo by default but can be unlocked, and can be remapped, we don't force taxa remapping from Argo model to all.

- **EcoTaxa classification :**

Object level filter granularity. We allow the user to get predicted and validated binned. We will call the EcoTaxa endpoint:

https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/api/docs#/objects/get_object_set

And not “summary” endpoint. It will allow us to show to the data consumer the object's main measurements metadata : Area, Area excluded, Major, Minor and Mean grey (Txo.display_name Fre.area). We may need evolutions of available filters of search in EcoTaxa.

So we want :

[sample, bin, taxon, concentration, biovolume, status]

OR

[bin, start size, end size, concentration]

As ODV users told us that flexibility of the accepted format in terms of row/column organisation in ODV software is limited, we choose to propose two export format one ODV and one TSV with the same info but organised differently.

Users can export in TSV format (optimised for code base utilisation) or ODV format (optimised for Ocean Data View ootb based utilisation).

When multiple projects are selected there could be different taxonomy levels depending on the project, so, in the default export we use the finest taxonomy level at the level of each project and we leave it to the data consumer to modify it post export.

Then we propose a filtering option of remapping categories in a modal in explore mode (We don't want the user to retype them each time, can we store them or collect remapping from EcoTaxa keep in mind but not a priority)

- **CTD** : as imported

Remote data

If there is some ARGO remote data then download data from them. :

<https://app.clickup.com/t/860q8anu6>

Historize exports

Exports will produce for each concerned project an export history data in the db. It will store information like : project id, export history date, exportator, nb sample exported.

Format uses for dataset UVP5 (idea)

UVP5_export summary formats

17. Administration

Administrators will have access to a specific menu tab named **Admin** containing the following subsections:

- **Quick Access** : will contain **statistics** (number of projects, users, thumbnails and data exports) with the ability to define a time period (all the time, last week, last year); **quick links** to more development oriented components (docker containers, docs etc.), last tasks in error and other **recurring actions**.

- **Users** : This tab will contain a table of the list of all users (User id, Name, Email, Organization, Country, Creation date, Manage, Contribute, Account status) The Manage and Contribute columns will contain the list of project IDs where the user has permissions.

The admin will be able to filter on each col, he will be able to select one or many user and perform actions on them, such as :

- Remove from all projects
- Add admin
- Remove admin
- Active
- Deactive
- Tasks
- Projects

- **Projects** : the Project tab will contain a table with the list of all projects (Title, Instrument, EcoTaxa Project, RootFolder, Nbr Sample, Managers, Members). The administrator user will be able to filter and sort on all that attributes, in order to facilitate his search for projects according to the criteria he has chosen.

The table will allow multiple selection and launching of grouped actions such as :

- Delete
- Remove all members
- Remove all annotators
- Users
- Tasks

- **Tasks** : the Task tab will contain a table with the list of all tasks (Label, Owner, Status, Progress, Message, Creation, Last update). The administrator user will be able to filter and sort on all that attributes, in order to facilitate his search for task according to the criteria he has chosen.

The table will allow multiple selection and launching of grouped actions such as :

- Delete
- Stop
- Restart
- Users
- Projects

He will also be able to open a task details page.

- **Updates** : The updates tab will allow the administrator to display a message banner to notify users of a service interruption for an upcoming update.

18. Tasks

A task will have a **type**, a **status** and optionally a **log**.

The **type** can be :

- Import
- Export
- Update
- Delete

The **status** can be :

- Processing
- Error
- Success

The actions allowed on the task are :

- Stop

All that types of tasks will be triggered by an API call objects will have the following format :

URL: /project/{project_id}/import

```
{
  "root_folder_path": "str",
  "CTD": {
    "ftp_file_sub_paths": [
      "str"
    ]
  },
  "Particles": {
    "ftp_folder_sub_paths": [
      "str"
    ]
  },
  "EcoTaxa": {
    "EcoTaxa_info": {
      "EcoTaxa_project_id": "int",
      "EcoTaxa_access_token": "str"
    },
    "ftp_folder_sub_paths": [
      "str"
    ]
  }
}
```

URL : /project/{project_id}/update/

```
{
  "root_folder_path": "str",
  "CTD": {
    "ftp_file_sub_paths": [
```

```
        "str"
    ]
},
"Particles": {
    "ftp_folder_sub_paths": [
        "str"
    ]
}
}
```

URL : post /project/{project_id}/delete/

URL : /sample_set/delete/

```
{
  "sample_id_list": ["int"]
}
```

URL : /sample_set/export/

```
{
  "sample_id_list": ["int"]
}
```

=> Define export format in export part

19. Migration

Existing EcoPart projects

The migration of old projects living on EcoPart is needed.

There are currently 534 projects. There are 57 unique project owners for these projects. There are projects for 5 unique instruments : liss, MOCNESS, uvp5, uvp6, uvp6remote.

The migration strategy will be as follow :

1- List all project in EcoPart

2- Based on the first list, establish the list of project to migrate :

- Filter and remove test project
- Identify empty projects (no samples) and ask the owner if we need to migrate them, if no answer does not migrate.

3- For projects we want to migrate :

- Check if the Root folder specified in the project is still available,
 - a. If yes, list all the samples imported in the old EcoPart project and verify that no one is missing from specify Root folder,
 - i. If there are no missing samples, recreate the project in new EcoPart and import only these samples from the root folder.
 - ii. If there are missing samples, contact the owner of the project and try to get the missing one.
 - b. If the root folder isn't correct then : try to contact the owner of the project to get the original data folder.

List EcoPart projects that are linked to the same EcoTaxa project and contact the owner to ask if we can split projects in EcoTaxa.

List potential subsets of EcoTaxa project linked to an EcoPart project and contact the owner to ask if we can update his subset to match the migration.

20. RGPD

The user will be able to completely suppress his account, but before that he will be asked to remove himself from any project where he is a member or manager.

21. Documentation

We will use the MUI [drawer component](#) as a documentation panel to document all application fields and functionalities. It will be filled as we go along with the development of the interface pages.

22. Translation

The translation will be handled from the beginning of the project even if we will not translate the app right away. We will use [BabelEdit](#), [i18next](#). The language will be determined by browser preferences.

If a translation key is not found or the browser language is not among our available translations EN will be used.

[i18next](#) allows us to integrate variables into a translation. Translations are stored in `/locales/en/translation.json`.

As the translations will be stored on the backend side we will need to wrap the app into a `React.suspense` component to prevent loading errors.

23. Automated testing

- **Unit Testing** : having good coverage of unit testing reduces the regression. Unit testing should be mandatory for any features that are being developed.
- **Integration and API Testing** : we will probably follow API-driven architecture for development. API testing acts as middle-level or integration testing, and it's easy to achieve.
- **UI Testing** : The UI testing mostly validates the styles, layouts, alignments, fonts, etc. The well-defined UI testing helps to reduce UI bugs and provides a smoother User experience (UX). All of this considered, we will not go for UI testing at least at the beginning cause it's not a functional priority.

- **End to End Testing** : The end-to-end testing mostly replicates the user behaviour using simulation. This is the exact replacement for manual testing. We should define end-to-end test cases for most important use cases defined at the beginning of the document.

Desire target coverage percentage :

Backend : >80%

API testing coverage : >80%

Front end, in a second time : if possible around 60%

We will use the [Jest](#) testing framework.

Useful link and tutorials :

[Unit testing for NodeJS using Jest Framework: Tutorial](#)

[How to Test React Components using Jest and Enzyme](#)

[Testing React Components with Jest and Enzyme- In Depth](#)

24. Technologies

Front

React (to do : next, redux?)

TypeScript

MUI

Back

Node.js

Express

TypeScript

CI/CD

Husky

Docker

Automated testing :

gh-actions

[Jest](#)

[Coveralls](#)

25. Analytics

Ecopart will integrate google analytics.

22. Annexes

Meetings notes

Meeting dev 21 decembre 2023

Externally validated : TODO

Meeting argo 11 decembre 2023

Chaque variable a son pendant var var_qc var_adjusted var_adjusted_qc

RT

-> 24h max après que le flotteur ait fait surface

2 niveaux :

- R variable
- A variable ajustée

Delay mode

-> fait plus tard

Echelle de notation:

1 bon

2 probablement bon

3 probablement mauvais

4 mauvais

5 donnée changée

...

Echelle de notation du Profil :

A

B

C

D

E

F

Les QC à ajouter dans EcoPart

-> pour les données de structure argo ajouter un qc par variable, modifiable et réexportable vers argo

-> pour les autres données

-> Générer le QC à la volée à l'export en fonction des bins sélectionnées

-> OU/ET à l'import lancer des QC automatique sur des bin fix (5m)

Meeting November 17 : JO LIONEL MARC CAMILLE JULIE

-> add contact in managers list: done

-> solution to request protected EcoTaxa resources :

- + Super user EcoPart

- + We can create an EcoTaxa endpoint that returns directly the :

 - vol and depth (pressure) : to compute the concentration

- + User status + license to get the data

 - + find the issue GH : [511](#), [510](#), [240](#), [244](#)

 - +When the EcoPart project becomes open, it implies that the EcoTaxa project becomes open (ccby) so : anyone authenticated can collect the data

 - + if the EcoTaxa project is “Visible” and the user is a member of the EcoPart project, he will be able to collect the EcoTaxa classification data without any right or identification in EcoTaxa.

-> Storage:

- EcoPart will store all raw data; Images will be stored also in raw

- Export by images; same export for all UVP(5/6): UVP6 export for everyone

-> Modification of metadata :

- Ecopart portable => (!) data retention

- If metadata editing in EcoPart => propagated to text file (raw data)? Yes but take into account a versioning to ensure the durability of the original data. Ex versioning of the header file?

- (!) duplication of data between the server here and in the app EcoPart storage
=> conclusion : we are going towards a modification of the project metadata directly inside the EcoPart app but we will go progressively so V1 will be without metadata editing.

Meeting February 28 : JO MARC JULIE

EXPORTS

=> on ne garantit pas le backup donc pas d'export du dossier entier

↳ RAW data (granularité des filtres **sample**)

- **Summary** => homogène entre les deux exports.
Format : à définir
- **LMP** : Date et bru et meta de uvp5
Format uvp6 par default
+ Meta (header) à modifier pour ajouter les unités par exemple
- **EcoTaxa classification** : format tsv (sans histo) 1 ligne par objet
(*) correspond à un export par défaut dans EcoTaxa (*)
-> 1 req par projet
=> images ou pas : NON.
Custom export, pas d'images, splitté par sample pour être cohérent avec les lpm

↳ Binned data (granularité des filtres **objet**)

- **Summary** : => homogène entre les deux exports.
Format : à définir
- **LMP** : *size spectra*,
Choix des bin (time/depth) => directement dans le explore
TSV & ODV
=> besoin des classes de taille détaillé par instrument.
Le fichier en sortie contiendra les colonnes de classe de taille utile seulement, si un count est à 0 mettre 0. Si absence de valeur pour un instrument mettre NA (en fonction de la plus petite classe de taille visible par l'instrument concerné) => facilite le travail en aval.

- **EcoTaxa classification** : granularité des filtres niveau objet, biné prédit validé en appelant le endpoint :

https://EcoTaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/api/docs#/objects/get_object_set

(Txo.display_name Fre.area)

Et pas summary : car bins différents par projet? (plus très sûre de ce qu'on a dit)

On voudra donc :

[sample, bin, taxon, concentration, biovolume, status]

OU

[bin, taille de début, taille de fin, concentration]

=> demander à des utilisateurs ODV quel souplesse ce format offre en terme d'organisation lignes/colonnes

Niveau taxonomique différents en fonction des projets -> donc nous dans l'export par défaut on utilise le niveau de taxo le plus fin au niveau de chaque projet et on laisse le soin au data consumer de les modifier post export.

Ensuite on propose une option de filtrage de remapping de catégories dans une modal à l'explorer. (pb : on doit les retaper à chaque fois? On peut les stocker? , récupérer des remapping depuis EcoTaxa ...)

=> dans le cas des uvp6 remote (ARGO) netcdf

-> RAW : from uvp6 remote déjà biné

-> Binned data : bin argo par défaut mais déblocable, remapping possible on impose pas celui du model à tous!

Btn export selected samples, en fait non export objects?

A ajouter aux filtres : remapping catégories + choix de bin temps et depth => fait

/!\ techno pour les graphs, prendre en compte la fuite potentielle de données par le navigateur :

Explore : classes réduites

Export : classes détaillées ou On laisse le choix? => je suis pour qu'on laisse pas le choix et qu'on mette toutes les classes détaillées

Ajouter categorie de myriam ?

1 µm, 1.26 µm, 1.59 µm, 2 µm, 2.52 µm, 3.17 µm, 4 µm, 5.04 µm, 6.35 µm, 8 µm, 10.1 µm, 12.7 µm, 16 µm, 20.2 µm, 25.4 µm, 32 µm, 40.3 µm, 50.8 µm, 64 µm, 80.6 µm, 102 µm, 128 µm, 161 µm, 203 µm, 256 µm, 323 µm, 406 µm, 512 µm, 645 µm, 813 µm, 1.02 mm, 1.29 mm, 1.63 mm, 2.05 mm, 2.58 mm, 3.25 mm, 4.1 mm, 5.16 mm, 6.5 mm, 8.19 mm, 10.3 mm, 13 mm, 16.4 mm, 20.6 mm, 26 mm

Meeting september 4 : CAMILLE MARC JULIE

Metadata -> Où les lire?

Dans ecodata ou dans raw?

Dans l'onglet "List importables samples" : on listera les samples grâce au header. On mettra un warning la place de l'icone import qui empêche d'importer si :

- On voit que dans les metadata dans le sample raw associé, le sample n'est pas processé,
- On voit que le fichier dans le sample raw est missing. (il manque les images ou il manque les particules)

À l'Import lors de la phase de validation des données on ira se baser sur ecodata/work. **Checks à définir avec Marc PICHERAL et Camille CATALANO.**

Si la validation passe, les samples sont bien importées dans l'appli (la tâche d'import se termine ici). Les samples sont en attente de validation manuelle du QC sur les données.

Quid de leur visibilité dans cet état?

Pas besoin de my file on continuera d'utiliser le ftp car ecopart reste ici.

Meeting september 4 : CAMILLE MARC JULIE - IMPORT RAW

- Backup raw au niveau du projet.

-> Avec option skip already imported. Donc on ne delete pas les manquants, on importe tout ou juste les nouveaux en fonction de cette option.

- Export raw backupé projet. (par projet uniquement)

-> zip des folders raw, meta et config

-> l'ajouter à l'UI

-> l'ajouter aux specs

->Et créer le sprint 11 sur ce thème

Définition des niveaux de données :

L0-a : raw raw

L0-b : raw traité (ecodata ou work) avec qc flag PENDING

L1-a : raw traité + QC visuel

L1-b : ajouts d'autres qc.. Tbd

Meeting novembre 22 : CAMILLE MARC JULIE

Si metadata first end image ont changés on delete et ré-importe, si pas changées on update juste les metadata

Dans le cas d'un uvp6 statique on ajoute plus tard la pression. Dernière ligne du fichier header. Si cette colonne a changée.

-> a se souvenir quand on implémente le QC : quand seul les metadata ont changées on ne le relance pas. Si non on le relance (seulement le cas first end image qui ont changés)